

DIRECTION DETECTION OF SELECTED PHARMACEUTICAL STOCKS USING MACHINE LEARNING

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Abstract: A direction is a trend that the market follows throughout a specific time period. Trends can be both upward and downward, corresponding to bullish and bearish markets. Direction detection is an excellent way to predict how the market will move in the future, and it can assist investors in shifting the odds in their favor while trading. Understanding the direction of the stock market is of the utmost importance for any approach that investors take in the market. An investor could suffer substantial losses if invested in a stock without knowing its direction and it happens to be in a prolonged slump. Investor may buy high and sell low if they do not grasp the stock's history and current direction. There are many algorithms available to investors that can pinpoint the exact closing price of any stock without revealing the direction of the closing price. This study uses a variety of machine learning classification methods to try and forecast the direction of the given stock. This study's goal is to create the best models possible by combining several modelling techniques and investigating innovative ways to reduce direction prediction mistakes. The dataset includes daily closing prices of a stock for the previous 22 years, and different models are employed to predict direction changes based on 2% and 4% differences in percentage change in close price. The rule classifies these changes as either positive or no change. To enhance prediction accuracy, technical analysis indicators like Average True Range (ATR) and Volume Weighted Average Price (VWAP) are also integrated as feature variables. The class Imbalance problem is solved using the SMOTE over-sampling technique. Multiple classification models are developed to assess their predictive accuracy, with the Random Forest (RF) model showing the highest accuracy of 91% for 2% variation and 96% for 4% variation in closing price. Also, Neural Networks provided the next best results in predicting stock price direction with 85% accuracy for 2% variation and 95% accuracy for 4% variation. The key takeaway from this is the significant utility of diverse classification modeling techniques in effectively forecasting the direction of closing prices for the stock in question.

Keywords: Direction Detection, Pharmaceutical sector, Stock Market, ATR, VWAP, Classification Models, Net Returns

1.Introduction

The principles of a free-market economy are strongly supported by the stock market. It functions as a significant financial tool that enables firms and businesses to obtain cash via investments made by the public. It is anticipated that those who put their money into company shares would receive returns in the form of dividends and an increase in stock value. In addition to improving their financial situation, this promotes the expansion of the business whose stocks are traded publicly. Even when dealing with discount brokers, there's usually a fee associated with each buying and selling transaction when trading stocks through a broker. As trading frequency increases, these fees can significantly erode any potential gains, as highlighted by (Huang et al., 2021). Live validations appear challenging due to various factors like price fluctuations, limited market-moving news, and ongoing market noise. Therefore, it might be a practical approach to consider and implement various popular stock evaluation methods (Shah et al., 2019).

Fundamental and technical analysis have undergone a few technological developments that help traditional investors make better decisions. The open, close, high, and low volumes of the stock under examination are the foundation for a few technical indicators, including momentum, trend, volatility, and volume indicators. The ordinary man's prospects are also improved by fund managers and investment managers thanks to algorithmic trading and other automated trading advances that are already available. The unguarded speculations have caused significant losses for average investors and damaged the stock market's reputation due to some unfair practices that are present in the current financial markets, but there has been ample evidence of market manipulation and fraudulent practices by some dubious advisory firms.

The stock market's high volatility has made it a fresh subject of exploration for researchers, traders, investors, and enterprises. With the increasing adoption of machine learning methodologies, there is a potential to make market predictions, as highlighted (Haque et al., 2022). The necessity to address uncertainties in fundamental and technical analysis, coupled with significant advancements in modeling techniques, has motivated numerous scholars to explore innovative methods for predicting stock values. Cutting-edge techniques are now being applied in the prediction of stock prices (Rouf et al., 2021). The study aims to underscore the advantages of machine learning and artificial intelligence in comparison to both manual and algorithmic trading. Its scope

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encompasses the exploration of unsupervised and multiple supervised classification techniques with the objective of predicting upward price movements in any given stock. While investors have access to numerous algorithms that can precisely predict a stock's closing price, this thesis takes a distinctive approach by endeavoring to predict the direction of the closing price for any stock under examination. Furthermore, it intends to assess the prediction performance using evaluation metrics specific to the modeling techniques employed in this Study.

This study is focused on the pharmaceuticals sector, daily trading data from the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) spanning from the years 2000 to 2022 for three prominent companies: Sun Pharma, Dr. Reddy's Laboratories, and Cipla have been utilized. Notably, the pharmaceutical industry is Studied to experience a significant growth rate of 7 to 8% by the year 2024-25.

2. Review of Literature

The stock market plays a significant role in the financial sector, providing companies with opportunities to enhance their financial prospects. In exchange for investors' investments in company stocks, they can reap profits from dividends and upward movements in stock prices. The literature review begins by examining the concepts of technical and fundamental stock analysis. It then delves into how algorithmic trading, based on both fundamental and technical indicators, aids investors in their decision-making processes. Additionally, it underscores the advantages of employing machine learning and artificial intelligence in contrast to traditional algorithmic trading. The review also covers unsupervised learning and various supervised classification techniques applied in this thesis. Finally, it assesses the literature pertaining to the confusion matrix, exploring different metrics used for evaluating the modeling techniques utilized in this Study.

Expanding on this topic, algorithmic trading is a systematic approach to trading that eliminates subjective judgments made by human traders, relying instead on computer programs (Hansen, 2020). Nevertheless, regulatory authorities have imposed limitations on algorithmic trading in response to allegations of market manipulation (Mukerji et al., 2019).

Machine learning and artificial intelligence are becoming more prevalent in the realm of business analytics. Nevertheless, it is recommended that exploratory data analysis be conducted to enhance one's understanding of the data (Mukerji et al., 2019). Some studies have employed a combination of supervised and unsupervised machine learning methods for predictive modeling in the securities market and have found that both types of models can generate reasonably accurate predictions (Digitalcommons@usu & Alhomadi, n.d.).

The stock market is influenced by numerous factors of varying magnitudes and complexities. As a result, different types of analyses, specifically technical and fundamental analysis, are conducted to make investments in the stock market. Fundamental analysis is instrumental in recognizing and executing short positions, involving the sale of shares from companies that exhibit downward trends and subsequently covering these positions by repurchasing shares when these companies show upward trends (Elbially, 2019). While obtaining funding through debt can be profitable, it carries significant risks if the company fails to meet its obligations (Anjani & Syarif, 2019). Investors believe that historical data can provide insights into future price movements (Fajareon & Sornil, 2019). Fundamental analysis aids in assessing the quality of stocks, and subsequently, technical analysis, which is conducted later, performs more effectively on stocks with strong fundamental characteristics. Technical analysis can identify patterns related to factors like trading volume and price movements (Sandeep & Mtech, n.d.).

Furthermore, in this Study, a variety of supervised classification machine learning techniques have been employed and assessed, including Logistic Regression (LR), Naïve Bayes (NB), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), and Neural Networks (NN). LR is chosen over linear regression when the target variable is categorical, either nominal or ordinal, rather than numeric (Al-Bairmani & Ismael, 2021). RF is a highly adaptable ensemble learning algorithm suitable for datasets with non-linear patterns and is particularly effective for medium to large-sized datasets (Schonlau & Zou, 2020). The Naïve Bayes classifier utilizes a sequence of probabilistic calculations to determine the most appropriate classification for a given set of data within a specific problem domain (Yang, 2018). NN (Neural Networks) yields best results in technic analysis-based method for forecasting stock market trends (Singh et al., 2022). Support Vector Machines (SVM) function effectively and achieve higher accuracy compared to a Binary Classifier (Carter et al., 2022).

Multiple classification algorithms need to be constructed for the dataset, and afterward, these algorithms must undergo testing. The confusion matrix serves as a comprehensive representation of predicted versus actual values in a single matrix. It assesses various performance metrics, including accuracy, precision, and recall (Markoulidakis et al., 2021). Accuracy gauges the model's precision based on its correct classification of true positives and true negatives in the dataset. AUC (Area Under the Curve) compares the rates of false positives and true positives in the dataset (Silva & Naranjo, 2020).

3.Design Framework

3.1. Problem Statement

A direction is a trend that the market follows throughout a specific time. Trends can be both upward and downward, corresponding to bullish and bearish markets.

An investor has to endure substantial losses if invested in a stock without knowing its direction and it happens to be in a prolonged slump. Investors may buy high and sell low if they do not grasp the stock's history and current direction.

Stocks can be quite volatile, and if investors don't understand their trends, they may be caught off guard by unexpected price movements. This might result in emotional decisions, such as selling during a slump or buying at the pinnacle of a boom. Also, timing the market is difficult, and investor may not know whether to buy or quit a position if they do not grasp a stock's trend. Investors may miss out on possibilities or invest at an inopportune time.

The direction of the stock indicates whether the trend is continuing or reversing. These are useful trading inputs. A solid understanding of the market's fundamental direction might increase the likelihood of trading success. To enhance chances of success, a competent trader should always know the direction of the market. Direction detection can also be used to extrapolate future price movements and serve as a warning mechanism when a trend is about to reverse. Investors can forecast future price swings by looking at the direction.

Investors have access to a variety of algorithms that can determine the precise closing price of any stock without disclosing the direction of the closing price. When dealing with limited data to construct a model, it can lead to underfitting scenarios that compromise the accuracy of our machine learning model. Conversely, when attempting to account for all possible data variations, both existing and non-existing, overfitting scenarios in regression models can also detrimentally impact test data accuracy, even if the trained data performs well. This situation underscores the need for not solely relying on algorithms for the quantitative prediction of a stock's exact closing price.

This Study uses a variety of machine learning classification methods to try and forecast the direction of the given stock.

3.2. Objectives of the Study

The Study's goals are as follows, and they are based on the problem description from the problem statement.

1. **Investigate Data Patterns:** Investigate the data patterns to have a full understanding of 22 years of pharmaceutical stocks. Following that, the data is organized, addressing class imbalance problem and features are added to it to improve the precision and sensitivity of the forecasting models.
2. **Build Classification models:** constructing appropriate models using various classification modeling techniques such as the LR Classifier, DT Classifier, RF Classifier, Naive Bayes Classifier, and Neural Network. The goal is to find a modeling algorithm that predicts price direction with maximum accuracy.
3. **Minimize the errors in predictions:** Investigate cutting-edge ways to reduce incorrect direction prediction. Every forecasting approach has flaws, and because the stock market is volatile, there is more potential for errors. Given the prior data, it should be feasible to properly estimate whether the price would increase or decrease using the precision, recall, and accuracy measures used in classification modeling techniques.
4. **Derive Insights:** Examining the confusion matrix to see how well the model performs in terms of true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives.

3.3. Study Methodology

The Study methodology that is being used and efforts for continuous improvement that will be made while working on the Study are more thoroughly examined in this section.

The Study has adopted the Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM) framework, which is divided into six key stages as shown in Figure 1, business understanding, data understanding, data preparation, modeling, evaluation, and deployment.

Figure 1: CRISP -DM Process Diagram(Wikipedia - CRISP-DM, 2023)

Figure 1 Illustrates the CRISP-DM framework, which consists of six distinct phases. Threads originating from the "Business Understanding" phase are gathered to create a comprehensive overview and blueprint for the subsequent phases of the data mining process.

1. **Business Understanding:** A fundamental and technical analysis of stocks is conducted to justify our choice to employ a specific stock dataset for this Study.
2. **Data Understanding:** This section of the study is to perform univariate analysis and bivariate analysis on a variety of feature variables to understand more about their characteristics.
3. **Data Preparation:** The Data Preparation process involved adding new features, filling in missing values, and scaling the data using Standard Scaler before the dataset could be used for modeling. The class imbalance problem is the target variable is addressed using the SMOTE technique.
4. **Modeling:** Several classifiers, like the LR classifier, DT classifier, RF classifier, NB classifier, and NN classifier, are used to develop predictive models during the "Modeling" phase.
5. **Evaluation:** The results of the various modeling methodologies used in the "Evaluation" phase are carefully examined, and their performance and efficiency are evaluated.
6. **Deployment:** The creation of a front-end Application Programming Interface (API) for the deployment dashboard is the final step in the "Deployment" phase, enabling the practical application of the research and insights from our study.

The CRISP-DM can operate in a very flexible manner (it can go back and forth between whole separate phases). The CRISP-DM approach itself is not one-time. Every technique has the potential to be a fresh learning experience that teaches new things as it goes along and may lead to new business questions (Wikipedia - CRISP-DM, 2023).

3.3 Business Understanding

This study's objective is to forecast the direction of the selected pharmaceutical stock and determine whether the net returns on invested capital based on the categorization model are higher than bank interest returns, which carry the same risk as investing in the stock market. The section involves the collection of all pertinent data and draws conclusions by conducting technical analysis of Cipla stock (Cipla, 2023), Sun Pharmaceutical Industries Limited (Sun Pharma, 2023) and Dr. Reddy's Laboratories (Dr. Reddy's, 2023) stocks, are the datasets under consideration for this study.

Fundamental Analysis:

Cipla Pharmaceuticals, founded in 1935 and headquartered in Mumbai, India, is a multinational pharmaceutical company with a presence in 86 countries and 47 manufacturing facilities worldwide. It ranks as the third-largest drug producer in India, boasting a 52-week high of 1277.90 and a low of 852.0. Sun

Pharmaceutical Industries Limited, established in 1983 and headquartered in Mumbai, India, operates globally with 44 manufacturing locations. With a 52-week high of 1169.70 and a low of 856.80, it is a significant player in the pharmaceutical industry. Dr. Reddy's Laboratories Limited, headquartered in Mumbai, India, and founded in 1984, is another prominent multinational pharmaceutical company with a presence in Hyderabad. It too operates on a global scale, with 44 manufacturing facilities. Dr. Reddy's Laboratories has experienced a 52-week high of 5989.70 and a low of 3997.00.

Technical analysis of Cipla, Sun Pharma and Dr. Reddy's stock:

Over the course of 14 days, the Relative Strength Index (RSI) is interpreted as follows: If the RSI falls within the range of 25-45, it indicates a downward trend of the stock. When the RSI falls within the 45-55 range, it signals sideways movement. An RSI within the 55-75 range suggests an upward trend. An RSI below 25 signifies that the stock is oversold, while an RSI exceeding 75 implies the stock is overbought. Presently, the RSI for Cipla stock stands at 39.35, indicating a downward trend. Sun Pharma's RSI is at 65.62, indicating upward trend, and Dr. Reddy's stock has an RSI of 52.69, also signalling sideways movement. These RSI values provide insights into the current trends of these stocks.

By deducting the exponential moving averages of the last 26 days from the previous 12 days, MACD is calculated. The stock will be heading upwards if the MACD is bigger than 0 and greater than 9 days of exponential moving averages. And declining trend in a stock if both the MACD and the nine-day exponential moving averages are less than zero. The MACD for the Cipla stock is at 21.87. Sun Pharma's MACD is at 4.48, while Dr. Reddy's MACD is -0.11.

Over a span of 20 days, the Stochastic indicator derives its insights from the position of the close price within the high-low range, offering valuable information about a stock's momentum. Here is how to interpret it: A Stochastic value falling within the range of 55-80 indicates that the stock is on an upward trend. If the value falls between 45 and 55, it signifies a sideways trend. In the range of 20-45, the stock is in a downward trend.

When the Stochastic value exceeds 80, it suggests that the stock is overbought, while a value below 80 indicates oversold conditions. Presently, the Stochastic reading for Cipla stock stands at 51.38, signifying a sideways trend. Considering this, investors may find it prudent to exercise patience, waiting for the Stochastic indicator to display a lower value before making investment decisions. Sun Pharma's Stochastic value is currently 61.15, indicating an upward trend. For Dr. Reddy's stock, the Stochastic reading is 13.78, signifying overbought conditions. Investors in this scenario might contemplate waiting for the Stochastic indicator to register a lower value before taking any significant actions. These Stochastic readings serve as crucial guides for investors, providing insights into the prevailing trends in these stocks.

3.4 Data Understanding

Understanding data is a critical component of any research; this analysis uses daily trading data from Sun Pharma, Cipla, and Dr. Reddy from 2000 to 2022. BSE data are used in the analysis, which is obtained from Yahoo Finance. The following provides information on each column utilized in the Sun Pharma, Cipla, and Dr. Reddy's databases.

The datasets being considered for the study are denoted as "EQ," which signifies "Equity." It's important to note that within this series, intraday trading is indeed possible. This means that investors can engage in trading activities within the same trading day, making it suitable for short-term trading strategies.

Variables used in the study are listed below in Table 1:

Table 1 list of variables used in the Study

SL No.	Variables	Description
1	Average True Range (ATR)	The average true range (ATR) is a price volatility indicator showing the average price variation of assets within a given time period.
2	Close	This is the most crucial price because it represents the closing price of the market for the day. The close reflects intraday strength and serves as a reference price for the next day.
3	High	It is the price at which a stock is listed at its highest point in time
4	Low	The low represents the lowest value over time

5	Open	It is the value of the first trade that is recorded during the day's trading.
6	Percentage Change	The percentage change in a security's closing price is a way to measure the absolute percentage difference in its price compared to the closing price of the previous day. (Target Variable)
7	Volume	The number of shares traded between the daily open and close is referred to as the trading volume.
8	Volume Weighted Average Price (VWAP)	The average price for the security as measured by volume and value is called the volume-weighted average price.

In the study, two scenarios are taken into consideration. In the first scenario, the direction of the closing price is viewed as positive and appropriate for long trading in the stock market if the percentage change of the closing price is greater than 2%. If not, the closing price's direction is seen as negative and unsuitable for long trading on the stock market.

In the second scenario, when assessing the direction of a stock's closing price, it is considered favorable and suitable for long trading in the stock market if the percentage change in the closing price exceeds 4%. If it doesn't surpass this threshold, it is considered unfavorable and not conducive to extended stock market participation.

Figure 2 Target variable class distribution of Cipla, Sun Pharma, and Dr. Reddy's for 2% variation

As depicted in Figure 2, Cipla stock exhibits an upward movement on 594 occasions, making it suitable for long trading, while on 5,142 occasions, it does not display an upward trend. Sun Pharma stock exhibits an upwards movement on 730 occasions, making it suitable for long trading, while on 5,004 occasions, it does not display an upwards trend. Dr. Reddy's stock exhibits an upward movement on 603 occasions, making it suitable for long trading, while on 5,106 occasions, it does not display an upwards trend.

Figure 3 Target variable class distribution of Cipla, Sun Pharma, and Dr. Reddy's for 4% variation

As depicted in Figure 3, Cipla stock exhibits an upward movement on 151 occasions, making it suitable for long trading, while on 5,585 occasions, it does not display an upward trend. Sun Pharma stock exhibits an upwards movement on 186 occasions, making it suitable for long trading, while on 5,548 occasions, it does not display an upwards trend. Dr. Reddy's stock exhibits an upward movement on 131 occasions, making it suitable for long trading, while on 5,578 occasions, it does not display an upwards trend.

Figure 4 Close price of the Cipla, Sun Pharma, and Dr. Reddy's stock from the year 2000 to 2022

Figure 5 Distribution plot for the Cipla stock

Figure 6 Distribution plot for the Sun Pharma stock

Figure 7 Distribution plot for the Dr. Reddy's stock

As depicted in Figure 5, 6, and 7, it's observed that the mean value exceeds the median value in the data. This suggests a positively skewed distribution, which is consistent across all three stocks: Cipla, Sun Pharma, and Dr. Reddy's stocks. Notably, among these stocks, Sun Pharma appears to be the least volatile, followed by Dr. Reddy's. On the other hand, Cipla stocks exhibit the highest level of volatility when compared to the other two.

Figure 8 Scatter plot against the close price of Cipla stock from the year 2000 to 2022

Figure 9 Scatter plot against the close price of Sun Pharma stock from the year 2000 to 2022

Figure 10 Scatter plot against the close price of Dr. Reddy's stock from the year 2000 to 2022

As depicted in Figure 8, 9, and 10, a scatter plot has been created to visualize the relationship between all feature variables and the closing price of the Cipla, Sun Pharm, and Dr. Reddy's stocks. It is evident that there is a linear correlation between the independent variables and the target variable, with only a few minor outliers that have little impact. Except volume is one variable which does not have a linear relationship with close price.

Figure 11 Box plot for the Cipla, Sun Pharma and Dr. Reddy's from year the 2000 to 2022

As depicted in Figure 11, there is a significant gap between the 75th percentile and maximum values for most of the feature variables in all three stocks. This observation implies the presence of extreme values or outliers within our dataset.

The Cipla, Sun Pharma, and Dr. Reddy's stock-related feature variables are covered in this study as potential independent variables. The target or dependent variable used in the modeling techniques is the direction of Cipla, Sun Pharma, and Dr. Reddy's stock's closing prices percentage change. The target variable, which is the direction of the close price of the Cipla, Sun Pharma, and Dr. Reddy's stocks, is modelled using several modelling algorithms one at a time, and the results are compared in Leader Boards for the target variable.

3.5 Data Preparation

Data preparation is critical for model development and has an impact on model accuracy. There are a number of restrictions on the data that is taken from the BSE for the Cipla, Sun Pharma, and Dr. Reddy's equities that necessitate processing. These actions consist of the following:

Addressing Missing Values: One of the features, namely volume of trading exhibited less than 1% of missing values. Consequently, these rows must be removed due to their number of missing entries. The utilization missing value imputation methods should be avoided as they can potentially introduce bias by generating values that may not accurately represent trends within the dataset. This approach solely considers the individual variable, which may result in values that do not align with overall dataset patterns.

Feature Addition: Computed variables that will affect stock returns are included as new features to the dataset. The rolling periods for these moving averages are five, ten, twenty, and two hundred days are included. This will be helpful in assessing the results on the securities market. Along with the input feature, average true range values for 14days and volume are also added to create the categorization models.

Class Imbalance: Unbalanced data distribution occurs when observations in one class are significantly higher or lower than those in the other classes. This is evident in the data interpretation phase for both 2% and 4% variation target variables. Traditional ML methods favour the majority class and tend to disregard the minority class. They frequently misclassify the minority class relative to the majority class because they tend to exclusively forecast the majority class. In other words, if our dataset includes an unbalanced distribution of data, our model is more susceptible to situations where the recall for the minority class is zero or extremely low. One of the oversampling methods, known as SMOTE, is used to oversample the minority class to solve the imbalance problem. Positive cases are oversampled in the Study to overcome the imbalance problem.

Scaling of data: To achieve better performance with machine learning algorithms, it is important that features exhibit normal distributions and are on similar scales. Scikit-learn provides several preprocessing techniques such as MinMaxScaler, RobustScaler, StandardScaler, and Normalizer. The choice of methodology to deploy depends on the type of model being used and the characteristics of the feature values. StandardScaler is a commonly employed data scaling method. It assists in achieving a standardized distribution for features, wherein the mean becomes zero and the standard deviation becomes one. This scaling process involves subtracting the mean value of a feature from each data point and then dividing the result by the standard deviation of that feature. The objective is to rescale the features to fit within a specified range while maintaining the original shape of the data distribution.

4. Modeling

By assessing the accuracy of direction detection, it is possible to provide guidance to potential investors on whether to consider investing in a stock or not. Direction prediction accuracy is established by utilizing momentum, trend, volatility, and volume indicators as feature variables and constructing various classification models based on these indicators. Table 9.1 outlines the modeling approaches and evaluation criteria employed in this Study.

Table 2 Modelling Strategy and model evaluation rule

Modelling Strategy	Model Evaluation Rule
Positive trend prediction using Open, Close, Low, Close, Volume, VWAP and ATR	Percentage change in closing price > 2%, Positive Trend
	Percentage change in closing price > 4%, Positive Trend

Classification model on technical indicators:

The approach involves collecting the daily closing prices for the stock in question and organizing them in a table for the entire dataset. To construct the classification model, the percentage change in closing price is calculated. When the percentage change between consecutive closing prices exceeds 2%, the closing price direction is considered positive. Conversely, if the percentage change in closing price is less than 2%, the closing price direction for the stock is regarded as negative.

Likewise, when the percentage change between consecutive closing prices surpasses 4%, the closing price direction is classified as positive. Conversely, if the percentage change in closing price falls below 4%, the closing price direction for the stock is categorized as negative.

In the event of a negative change, typically, the recommendation to the investor would be to refrain from investing under such circumstances. Conversely, if there is a positive change, the investor would be advised to consider making an investment.

The goal is to assess how often the model correctly identifies positive changes through its predictions and how often positive changes occur in the actual data. This assessment will be used to determine the number of true positives correctly detected and the number of false positives predicted. A similar procedure will be applied to identify true negatives and false negatives. By evaluating prediction accuracy in this manner, it is possible to provide guidance to potential investors on whether to consider investing.

Furthermore, technical indicators such as VWAP (Volume Weighted Average Price) and ATR (Average True Range) are incorporated as features to construct a classification model. These features are combined with open, close, low, high, and volume variables to enhance prediction accuracy. Five distinct models are being developed based on two different conditions for three different stocks. The dataset is split, with 75% used for testing and 25% for training.

Several classification models, specifically LR Classifier (Logistic Regression Classifier), RF Classifier (Random Forest Classifier), SVM Classifier (Support Vector Machine Classifier), NB Classifier (Naive Bayes Classifier), and NN (Neural Networks), are implemented and their prediction accuracies are compared.

When the majority or all the thirty different models indicate the same direction, a decision regarding whether to invest or abstain from investing in a particular stock needs to be taken. For instance, if an investor puts \$10,000 into Cipla stock and the prediction suggests a positive change for the following day, this prediction process is iterated, let's say, 100 times. The aim is to evaluate the net gain or loss resulting from these repeated predictions.

The complete procedure is applied and evaluated using a completely different dataset to ensure that any stock in the stock market can utilize this same method to make predictions about whether to invest, which is a valuable tool. Daily trading data from the year 2000 to 2022 for Sun Pharma and Dr. Reddy's is employed to replicate the entire process that is originally implemented for Cipla stock.

4.1 Model Evaluation

The preceding section delves into the precision of stock forecasting through the application of classification models. In the present section, a variety of classification models are employed to predict the direction of the closing value for Cipla, Sun Pharma, and Dr. Reddy's stocks, and the prediction accuracy is evaluated using diverse error metrics. The analysis and results module scrutinizes all the outcomes obtained from these diverse models and identifies the most effective model in terms of minimizing prediction errors.

Table 3 Model evaluation using Logistic Regression (LR) for direction prediction

Model rule	Cipla	Sun Pharma	Dr. Reddy's
Percentage change > 2%	Accuracy:0.84 Precision:0.88 Recall:0.78	Accuracy:0.79 Precision:0.82 Recall:0.75	Accuracy:0.82 Precision:0.83 Recall:0.81
Percentage change > 4%	Accuracy:0.90 Precision:0.91 Recall:0.89	Accuracy:0.79 Precision:0.82 Recall:0.75	Accuracy:0.88 Precision:0.86 Recall:0.89

According to Table 3, Cipla stock has a maximum accuracy of 84% for 2% variance and 90% for 4% variation for the LR model.

Table 4 Model evaluation using Random Forest (RF) for direction prediction

Model rule	Cipla	Sun Pharma	Dr. Reddy's
Percentage change > 2%	Accuracy:0.91 Precision:0.91 Recall:0.92	Accuracy:0.88 Precision:0.88 Recall: 0.88	Accuracy:0.91 Precision:0.90 Recall:0.89
Percentage change > 4%	Accuracy:0.96 Precision:0.96 Recall:0.96	Accuracy:0.96 Precision:0.96 Recall:0.97	Accuracy:0.95 Precision:0.94 Recall:0.98

Table 4 shows that Cipla and Dr. Reddy's stocks have the best accuracy of 91% for 2% variation and Cipla and Sun Pharma stocks have the highest accuracy of 96% for 4% variation for the RF model.

Table 5 Model evaluation using Neural Network (NN) for direction prediction

Model rule	Cipla	Sun Pharma	Dr. Reddy's
Percentage change > 2%	Accuracy:0.85 Precision:0.79 Recall:0.95	Accuracy:0.81 Precision:0.81 Recall: 0.80	Accuracy:0.90 Precision:0.89 Recall:0.90
Percentage change > 4%	Accuracy:0.95 Precision:0.95 Recall:0.94	Accuracy:0.89 Precision:0.87 Recall:0.92	Accuracy:0.93 Precision:0.92 Recall:0.95

According to Table 5, using the NN model, Dr. Reddy's stock has the best accuracy of 90% for 2% variation and Cipla stock has the highest accuracy of 95% for 4% variation.

Table 6 Model evaluation using Support Vector Machine (SVM) for direction prediction

Model rule	Cipla	Sun Pharma	Dr. Reddy's
Percentage change > 2%	Accuracy:0.79 Precision:0.80 Recall:0.78	Accuracy:0.76 Precision:0.78 Recall: 0.72	Accuracy:0.73 Precision:0.74 Recall:0.73
Percentage change > 4%	Accuracy:0.88 Precision:0.89 Recall:0.87	Accuracy:0.84 Precision:0.85 Recall:0.82	Accuracy:0.85 Precision:0.83 Recall:0.88

According to Table 6, For the SVM model, Cipla stock has the maximum accuracy of 79% for 2% variation and 88% accuracy for 4% variation.

Table 7 Model evaluation using Naïve Bayes (NB) for direction prediction

Model rule	Cipla	Sun Pharma	Dr. Reddy's
Percentage > 2%	Accuracy:0.61 Precision:0.62 Recall:0.6	Accuracy:0.65 Precision:0.63 Recall: 0.70	Accuracy:0.58 Precision:0.58 Recall:0.66
Percentage > 4%	Accuracy:0.65 Precision:0.63 Recall:0.74	Accuracy:0.61 Precision:0.58 Recall:0.79	Accuracy:0.57 Precision:0.56 Recall:0.50

According to Table 7, Sun Pharma has the most accuracy of 65% for 2% variation and Cipla stock has the highest accuracy of 65% for 4% variation for the NB model.

From Table 4, making a direction prediction utilizing the given features RF has resulted in significant precision, recall, and accuracy for Cipla stock for both conditions in predicting the direction.

5. Deployment

The proposed outline of deployment strategy, as illustrated in Figure 12, will be undertaken to meet the business requirements of creating front-end API-based executable applications.

Figure 12 Deployment blueprint for direction prediction

Figure 13 Design of dashboard

Figure 13 provides additional visualization of the dashboard. According to the plan for upcoming tasks, the dashboard receives input from an API, which is generated from machine learning algorithms. The deployment will serve multi-label features and offer a comprehensive end-to-end User Interface.

6. Analysis and Results

The results encompass the amalgamation of all the models, and the following section provides a detailed analysis of the outcomes for Cipla, Sun Pharma and D. Reddy's stock.

Direction detection prediction using best classifier model:

Table 8 Model evaluation using RF for direction prediction

Model rule	Cipla	Sun Pharma	Dr. Reddy's
Percentage change > 2%	Accuracy:0.91 Precision:0.91 Recall:0.92	Accuracy:0.88 Precision:0.88 Recall: 0.88	Accuracy:0.91 Precision:0.90 Recall:0.89
Percentage change > 4%	Accuracy:0.96 Precision:0.96 Recall:0.96	Accuracy:0.96 Precision:0.96 Recall:0.97	Accuracy:0.95 Precision:0.94 Recall:0.98

Table 9 Model evaluation using NN for direction prediction

Model rule	Cipla	Sun Pharma	Dr. Reddy's
Percentage change > 2%	Accuracy:0.85 Precision:0.79 Recall:0.95	Accuracy:0.81 Precision:0.81 Recall: 0.80	Accuracy:0.90 Precision:0.89 Recall:0.90
Percentage change > 4%	Accuracy:0.95 Precision:0.95 Recall:0.94	Accuracy:0.89 Precision:0.87 Recall:0.92	Accuracy:0.93 Precision:0.92 Recall:0.95

Table 8 reveals that the RF classifier model has achieved the highest level of accuracy in direction detection compared to other modeling techniques such as LR, RF, SVM, and NN Modeling. This finding has been tested and confirmed using consecutive closing prices percentage change used as feature variable. Furthermore, NN classifier modeling has demonstrated the best precision, recall, and accuracy in predicted direction detection after RF classifier.

Value from a business standpoint:

In this scenario, modeling algorithms are applied to predict the direction of Cipla, Sun Pharma, and Dr. Reddy's stocks spanning a period of 22 years, with a train-test split ratio of 75% to 25%. If an investor, invest Rs. 10,000 for a year and estimate profits based on a 2% and 4% change in the close price while aiming for the highest precision in detecting true positives, then the following outcomes could be anticipated from Equation (1).

$$\text{Net Returns} = \frac{(p \times c \times n \times pr) - (p \times c \times m \times pr)}{(p \times c \times n \times pr)} \dots (1)$$

where,

n = True Positive Value

m = False Positive Value

pr = Precision

p = Percentage Change of Closing price

c = Capital Invested

Direction Prediction for 2% percentage change:

Regarding the features with the highest precision of 0.91 of Cipla stock for 2% variation, the confusion matrix offers details as presented in Figure 15 below:

Figure 15 Confusion Matrix for Cipla stock of RF model

Therefore, net returns are:

$$((0.02 \times 10000 \times 1206 \times 0.91) - (0.02 \times 10000 \times 119 \times 0.91)) / (0.02 \times 10000 \times 1206 \times 0.91) = 90.13\% \text{ returns}$$

Direction Prediction for 4% percentage change:

Regarding the features with the highest precision of 0.96 of Cipla stock for 4% variation, the confusion matrix offers details as presented in Figure 16 below:

Figure 16 Confusion Matrix for Cipla stock of RF model

Therefore, net returns are:

$$((0.04 \times 10000 \times 1344 \times 0.96) - (0.04 \times 10000 \times 60 \times 0.96)) / (0.04 \times 10000 \times 1344 \times 0.96) = 95.45\% \text{ returns}$$

Thus, the average returns achieved through positive direction prediction are significantly greater when contrasted with average stock market returns that typically fall within the range of 7.0% to 7.5% provided by bank interest returns.

6.1 Conclusions and Future Scope

The stock being considered day-to-day closing price is being used. These closing prices will be tallied over the whole dataset, and the percentage change will be computed and used as a goal variable for developing the classification model. The criteria for what constitute a shift in direction are being established. Two different classes of direction are being considered for the rule that will be followed for computing the direction change as either a positive change or no change: 2% difference and 4% difference.

In technical analysis, every technical indicator is used to create a variety of classification models. Based on the input dataset, all different kinds of technical indicators, including Open, High, Low, Close, Volume, VWAP, and ATR, may be used as feature variables, and various classification models can be developed to evaluate their predictive power. The prediction accuracy of different classification models, including LR Classifier, RF Classifier, NB Classifier, SVM Classifier, and NN, is compared using metrics such as precision, recall, f1-score, accuracy score, and ROC AUC Score.

To forecast the direction of the close price for the stock under examination, all thirty models that are built are considered. One must decide whether to buy or sell the stock when most of the different models, or all of them, move in the same direction.

This research is primarily concerned with applying classification algorithm Techniques to forecast the direction of the close price of the Cipla stock. Later, a similar approach is used to forecast the direction of the close price of additional banking sector equities, including the stock of Sun Pharma and Dr. Reddy's stocks. A deployment dashboard will be suggested in the future. The dashboard can be used to forecast the direction of the close price for any stock in the banking sector and accepts API as an input obtained by machine learning algorithms, as per the proposal for future assignments. The same method may be used to forecast purchase or sell decisions for any stock on the stock market, which is advantageous.

In terms of future directions,

1. **Real-Time Data Processing:** Implementing real-time data processing pipelines that use cutting-edge technology to perform data transformations, aggregations, and feature engineering to improve model accuracy.
2. **Taking Volatility into account:** It is critical to understand that the Study's premise of constant returns over time is unnecessarily simplistic and does not reflect reality. Stock returns are very time-sensitive, varying drastically during market collapses and surges. To solve this constraint, future research should investigate how advanced machine learning techniques may be used to distinguish between bullish and bearish regimes.
3. **Adaptability of the model:** The approaches used in this Study are adaptable to predicting close price directions in both regular and volatile market settings.
4. **Sentiment Analysis:** It may also be beneficial to do sentiment research using text analytics to forecast stock market returns.
5. **Development of deployment dashboard:** As a further stage, there is potential for the development of a deployment dashboard for practical use and consideration of an intelligent automated system for options trading. These future efforts will try to improve the accuracy and resilience of stock market prediction models.

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